

Agile-Merode

US & BDD prioritization example

This text comes as an online attachment with the paper

Monique Snoeck, Yves Wautelet, Agile MERODE: A Model-Driven Software Engineering Method for User-Centric and Value-Based Development", Software and Systems Modelling, 2022

The following User Stories pertain to the development of the MERLIN modelling tool (<https://www.merlin-academic.com>)

User Story 1

US1

As a user, I want to sort my OET

As there are different ways of sorting the OET, this US needs clarification. Ultimately, 4 ways of sorting the OET are required, each depicted by a corresponding button in the user interface of the OET-tab:

First button = Sort rows, putting the events in the same order as the order of their owners in the columns. As a result, the OET takes the form of a (nearly) diagonal matrix.

Second button = Sort columns alphabetically.

Third Button = Sort columns according to Bottom-Up Level.

Fourth Button = Sort columns according to Top-Down Level.

(See MERODE (Snoeck, 2014), p63 for the definition of Bottom-up and Top-down levels of object types.)

Translation to a set of BDDs

Given the OET Tab is active

When I click the "Sort TDL level" button

Then the columns in the OET are re-ordered so that master object types are always to the left of their dependent object types.

Given the OET Tab is active

When I click the "Sort BUL level" button

Then the columns in the OET are re-ordered so that master object types are always to the right of their dependent object types.

Given the OET Tab is active

When I click the "Sort columns" button

Then the columns in the OET are re-ordered so that master object types are alphabetically listed from left to right.

Given the OET Tab is active

When I click the "Sort rows" button

Then the rows in the OET are re-ordered so that events appear according to the order of their master object types in the columns, starting with the creating events, followed by the modifying events and then the ending events.

Prioritization

These BDDs have no prerequisites other than that the OET exists. The (re-)ordering of columns and rows in the OET facilitates the reading of the OET, especially in case of large models. Given that this US and BDD only work on visualization and do not require expansion of the domain model, it has been put in Sprint 2: Basics of OET (=visualizing elements that are created by default by the tool).

User Story 2

US 2

A. As a user, I want to add methods in the OET

B. As a user, when I add a method to the OET, I want the methods to be propagated according to the MERODE propagation rule.

Translation to BDDs

The **yellow** parts refer to preconditions, and the **green** parts to postconditions.

Given the OET Tab is active

When I click the "Add Event" button

Then a popup opens, and I am allowed to add an Event by giving it a Java-compliant name

(Creating an Owned method)

Given the OET Tab is active, the "Add Method" button is activated, and I have clicked on a cell in the OET

And I have chosen "OWNED" as provenance,

And there is no other object type that already owns this event

And "Propagate automatically when creating a method" is checked in model settings

When I click the "Save" button in the dialog box

Then the method is created

and for all master object types (direct and indirect) a corresponding A/M method is added for the same event

Given the OET Tab is active, the "Add Method" button is activated, and I have clicked on a cell in the OET

And I have chosen "ACQUIRED" as provenance,

And the method that needs to be propagated exists

And the dependency along which the to-be-propagated method should be propagated exists

And the propagated method does not yet exist

And the chosen type of the method complies with consistency rules

And "Propagate automatically when creating a method" is checked in model settings

When I click the "Save" button in the dialog box

Then A/* method is created and for all master object types (direct and indirect) a corresponding A/M method is added for the same event.

Prioritisation

This User Story contains two individual user stories. Automatic propagation to keep the model consistent at any time by having autocompletion of models is however a key feature of the tool, see (Snoeck, Michiels, & Dedene, 2003). Separating the two, with the possibility of handling US2B later than US2A is not a good idea: the second US in this set has actually a very high business value, so should be done right away. These User Stories should thus be grouped together and handled as one.

The preconditions and the postconditions of BDD2 and BDD3 refer to the associations that constitute the EDG and establish master-dependency relationships (see boldface text). Those relationships define the propagation paths along which a methods need to be propagated (see chapter 5 in (Snoeck, 2014)). There is, in other words, an architectural precedence constraint that requires this US to be planned after the EDG (part 2 of the MERODE meta-model) has been implemented. Given the complexity of this US and the precedence constraints, this US was handled in Sprint 6 (OET).

References

- Snoeck, M. (2014). *Enterprise Information Systems Engineering* (Vol. 141).
<https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-10145-3>
- Snoeck, M., Michiels, C., & Dedene, G. (2003). Consistency by construction: The case of MERODE. *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (Including Subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)*, 2814, 105–117. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-39597-3_11